

JAVASCRIPTDA O'ZGARUVCHILAR.

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Anotatsiya: JavaScript tilida o'zgaruvchilarni ishlatish mumkin va ularni nomlari bilan adreslash mumkin. O'zgaruvchilar globali va lokalli bo'lishi mumkin. Globali o'zgaruvchilar ssenariyning xoxlagan joyida ruxsati bo'lishi mumkin. Lokalli o'zgaruvchilarning xarakati esa e'lon qilingan o'zgaruvchilar ichidagi funksiyalar bilan chegaralangan. Basic dasturlash tili singari JavaScript ssenariysini yaratayotgan vaqtda avvaldan e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchilarni ishlatish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zgaruvchilar, ma'lumotlar tipi, operatorlar, funksiyalar.

Аннотация: Язык JavaScript может использовать переменные и адресовать их по имени. Переменные могут быть глобальными и локальными. Глобальные переменные могут быть разрешены в любом месте сценария. С другой стороны, поведение локальных переменных ограничено функциями внутри объявленных переменных. При создании сценария JavaScript, такого как базовый язык программирования, можно использовать переменные, которые ранее не объявлялись.

Ключевые слова: переменные, тип данных, операторы, функции,

Abstract: Variables can be used in JavaScript and can be addressed by name. Variables can be global or local. Global variables can be accessed anywhere in the script. The behavior of local variables is limited to functions inside declared variables. As with the Basic programming language, it is possible to use undeclared variables when creating a JavaScript script.

Keywords: variables, data types, operators, functions.

Java Script da xamma o'zgaruvchilar var kalit so'zi orqali e'lon qilinadi va quyidagicha ko'rsatilgan:

```
var MyHelloMsg;
```

O'zgaruvchi tipi o'zlashtiriladiki qachonki, unga biror bir qiymat o'zlashtirilsa, quyida avvaldan e'lon

qilinmagan matnli qator o'zgaruvchiga yozilmoqda:

```
MyMsg = "Salom!";
```

MyMsg o'zgaruvchi nomi o'zlashtirilgandan so'ng ruxsat beriladi.

O'zgaruvchi nomini tanlaganda, quyidagi oddiy qoidalarni eslab qo'yish kerak:

O'zgaruvchi nomi xarflardan yoki "_", "\$" belgilardan boshlanish kerak va faqat xarflardan, sonlardan va "_", "\$" belgilardan iborat bo'lishi kerak;

O'zgaruvchilar nomi JavaScript ning zaxiralangan kalit so'zlari bilar mos kelmasligi kerak.

Quyida JavaScript ning zaxiralangan kalit so'zlar keltirilgan:

Break	Case	Catch	Class	Continie
Debugger	Default	Delete	Do	Else
Export	Extends	False	Finally	For
If	Import	In	New	Null

Bu so'zlar orasida JavaScript tilida va uning rivojlanishida o'zlashtirish rejalashtirilmoqda.

O'zgaruvchining qiymatini o'zlashtirish

"=" o'zlashtirish operatori yordamida o'zgaruvchilar qiymati o'zlashtiriladi. Misol qilib o'uyidagi o'zgaruvchi keltirilgan va unda matnli qator yozilgan:

```
var MyHelloMsg;
```

```
MyHelloMsg = "Hello, world!";
```

MyHelloMsg sonli o'zgaruvchini dasturning xoxlagan joyida o'zlashtirish mumkin, misol uchun:

```
MyHelloMsg = 4;
```

Bu operator bajarilgandan so'ng o'zgaruvchi tipi o'zgaradi, shuningdek interpretatsiya jarayonida

brauzer xech qanday ogoxlantiruvchi xabarlarini yubormaydi.

O'zgaruvchini maxsus null qiymati orqali o'zlashtirish mumkin:

```
MyHelloMsg = null;
```

Bunday o'zlashtirish xech qanday tipda o'zgaruvchini belgilamaydi.

Xulosa.

JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilardan keng miqyosda foydalansa b'ladadi. Asosan ular Global yoki lokal b'ladadi. Bu ikki xil o'zgaruvchilar haqida yuqorida kerakli ma'lumotlar beril o'tilgan

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

- 1."JavaScript dasturlash tilida funksiyalar" avtori Rustamjon Jumayev
- 2.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Prospects for the development of professional training of students of professional educational institutions using electronic educational resources in the environment of digital transformation." *Academica Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.10 (2022): 158-162.
- 3.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "The value of open mass competitions in the process of digitalization of extracurricular activities of schoolchildren." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.10 (2022): 338-344.
- 4.Jo'rayev, Muzaffarjon. "Professional ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo uzvilik va uzliksizlikni ta'minlash o'quvchilari kasbiy tayyorgarligining muhim omili sifatida." *Zamonaviy dunyoda amaliy fanlar: Muammolar va yechimlar* 1.29 (2022): 43-46.
- 5.Juraev, M. M. "OA Qo'ysinov Description of the methodological basis for ensuring interdisciplinary continuity of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in vocational education." *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed* 7.10 (2021).
- 6.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" *Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY" in Vocational Education.* *JournalNX* 7.10: 223-225.
- 7.Khasanov, A. R. (2022). LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 217-223.

- 8.Khasanov, A. R. (2022). Development of information competence of future informatics teachers as a pedagogical problem. Open Access Repository, 9(12), 73-79.
- 9.Xasanov, A. R. (2021, May). USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 198-199).
- 10.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
- 11.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of Information and Information Technologies." Open Access Repository 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
- 12.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Experience Of Cambridge Curricula In Ensuring The Continuity Of Curricula In The Field Of "Computer Science And Information Technology" In The System Of Professional Education." The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research 3.11 (2021): 26-32.
- 13.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Theoretical and practical principles of improving the content of the pedagogical activity of ICT teachers of professional educational institutions in the conditions of information of education." (2022).
- 14.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." (2022): 9-11.
- 15.Melikyzievich, Siddikov Ilkhom, et al. "THE METHOD OF REFERENCE TESTS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF DIGITAL DEVICES." International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education 14.7 (2022).
- 16.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Designing an electronic didactic environment to ensure interdisciplinary integration in the teaching of Informatics and information technologies" during professional education." Confrencea 11.11 (2023): 78-82.
- 17.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." Open Access Repository 9.1 (2023): 93-101.
- 18.Juraev, M. M. "ZY Xudoyberdiyev Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the System of professional education." European Scholar Journal (ESJ)//ISSN (E): 2660-5562.
- 19.Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).
- 20.Ўразбаева, Маҳбуба Қадамбоевна. "АЁЛ ХАРАКТЕРИНИ ОЧИШДА БАДИИЙ НУТҚНИНГ ЎРНИ." GOLDEN BRAIN 1.1 (2023): 193-199.
- 21.Пардаева, Нигора Қўйсинбоевна. "АНБАР ОТИН "ЯККА БАЙТЛАР" И ҲАҚИДААЙРИМ МУЛОҲАЗАЛАР." ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ. 2020.
- 22.Bahodirovna, Shahodat Norova. "ARTISTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF REPETITION IN THE LANGUAGE OF THE WORK." Open Access Repository 9.11 (2022): 6-8.

23.Norova, Shahodat. "Similar units in askad mukhtor's tungaliklar." Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 11.12 (2021): 127-129.

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